

observation of earlier workers⁸. The stability constants of the metal chelates were determined using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-metric titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti⁴ from the plots of $\bar{n}$ vs pL . The values obtained are given in Table I.

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE METAL CHELATES OF N-m-TOLYL-p-METHOXY BENZO-HYDROXAMIC ACID WITH TRANSITION METAL IONS

Metal ion	$\log K_1 \pm 0.06$	$\log K_2 \pm 0.08$	$\log K_3 \pm 0.1$	$\log \beta_3$
Fe(II)	10.5	10.2	9.0	29.7
Fe(III)	10.7	10.5	9.1	30.3
Co(II)	10.2	7.0	6.2	23.4
Ni(II)	8.5	6.3	5.2	20.0
Cu(II)	10.4	9.2	6.1	25.7

($\log \beta_3$ = overall concentration formation constant)

It is evident from Table I that Fe(III), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) form 1 : 3 complexes with TMBA. Values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ obtained are given in the table. Formation of 1 : 3 complex in case of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) may be due to the expansion of the coordination sphere in 50% alcohol system. Literature says that expansion of the coordination sphere occurs most frequently with square planar complexes by the uptake of further ligand⁸. Sacconi *et al*⁶ observed the uptake of heterocyclic bases by biacetyl bisbenzoylhydrazene Ni(II) complex in benzene. Graddon and Watton⁷ investigated the reaction of the bis(β -diketonato) copper(II) complex with heterocyclic bases in different non-aqueous solvent where the expansion of coordination sphere occurred. Expansion in the coordination sphere is also reported in case of square planar dimethylglyoxime complex of cobalt(II)⁸.

The stability constants of the present metal chelates follow the order Fe(III) > Fe(II) > Cu(II) > Co(II) > Ni(II), which agrees with the Irving-Williams⁸ natural order, except Co(II), leading to the conclusion that the ligand used in the present investigations is a weak field one. The greater stability of Co(II) complex as compared to Ni(II) complex may be due to the additional stabilization acquired by Co(II) complex due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The high stability of cobalt complex also may be due to the higher oxidation state of cobalt in the complex⁹.

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Studies on Potentiometric Stability of Some Trivalent Metal Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-4'-N-Diethylaminoaniline

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In the present communication, complexation equilibria of metal complexes of Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-N-diethylaminoaniline have been studied potentiometrically. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by refluxing alcoholic solutions of equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine for about 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to obtain an analytically pure compound, m. p. 102° (observed). The purity of the compound was tested by tlc and elemental analysis. (Found : C, 79.40; H, 6.81; N 8.86. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{22}N_2O$; C, 79.24; H, 6.92; N, 8.80%).

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and perchloric acid of A. R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

Other experimental details are the same as in our earlier communication³.

Results and Discussion

The stability constants were calculated from the titration data by the method of Irving and Rossotti¹. The $\bar{n}_A$ values at various B values (pH meter readings) were determined and from the plot of $\bar{n}_A$ vs B (Fig. 1) the pK_1 corresponding to the

dissociation of phenolic OH and pK_2 corresponding to the association of proton to azomethine nitrogen were determined at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and 1.5, respectively. From the titration curves, $\bar{n}$ and pL values were also computed for metal-ligand systems and from $\bar{n}$ vs pL curves (Fig. 2) $\log K_1$ values for various metal complexes were determined by half integral method. All the values were further corroborated by the straight line plots of $\log(\bar{n}/1-\bar{n})$ vs pL . The most representative values are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-N-diethylaminoaniline.

Fig. 2. Metal-ligand systems of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-N-diethylaminoaniline.

TABLE 1

	$t=30^\circ$			$\mu=0.1 M$			
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
$\log K_1$	9.28	12.23	12.55	7.56	7.96	7.75	9.33
$\log K_2$	6.75	—	—	—	—	—	—

The order of stability of metal chelates is found to be $Pr^{3+} > Y^{3+} > Dy^{3+} > Sm^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Nd^{3+}$.

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Studies on Potentiometric Stability of Some Trivalent Metal Complexes with 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-4'-(4''-Morpholinyl)Aniline

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IN the present communication, complexation equilibria of metal complexes of Y^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} and Dy^{3+} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-(4''-morpholinyl)aniline have been studied potentiometrically. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and formation constants ($\log K_1$) of its metal chelates have been determined following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by refluxing alcoholic solution of equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine for about 2 hr. The crude product was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 202° (observed). The purity of the compound was tested by tlc and elemental analysis. (Found : C, 75.80 ; H, 6.10 ; N, 8.26. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{20}N_2O_2$; C, 75.90 ; H, 6.02, N, 8.13%).

All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and perchloric acid of A.R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations².

Other experimental details are the same as in our earlier communication³.

Results and Discussion

The stability constants were calculated from the titration data by the method of Irving and Rossotti¹. The $\bar{n}_A$ values at various B values (pH meter readings) were determined and from the plot of $\bar{n}_A$ vs B (Fig. 1) the pK_1 corresponding